

Biosome Technology: Recent Advancements in Preparation, Characterization, and Practical Applications

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ABSTRACT:

Bilosomes are also known as bile vesicles, which are Nano-vesicular delivery systems of non-ionic surfactants that contains bile salts in their membrane. Bilosomes have attracted a lot of attention recently, because of its potential for usage in a variety of applications. This article discusses a number of topics pertaining to the innovative vesicular method for targeted drug delivery systems termed bilosomes, which is based on bile salts. It contains details about the composition of bilosomes, formulation strategies, characterisation procedures and its applications including their use as drug delivery systems for hydrophobic drugs. Various nano-vesicular delivery technologies, including liposomes, nanoparticles, and niosomes, have been created to address the issues related to numerous drugs. Due to the challenges they confront in the gastrointestinal tract (GIT), including pH, bile salts, and metabolic enzymes, their usage is regrettably restricted to the oral route. Owing to these challenges, a novel method of encasing the drug, shielding it from stomach breakdown, and boosting its bioavailability has emerged which are bilosomes. Their chemical stability and vesicle elasticity, which allows them to pass through pores that are smaller than their diameters and pierce deeply through tissue layers, which are influenced by the presence of bile salts and non-ionic surfactants in their compositions.

KEY WORDS: Bilosomes, Film Hydration, Reverse Phase Evaporation, Ether Injection, Nano-vesicular drug delivery systems, non-ionic surfactant.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Artificial phospholipid vesicles are also known as bilosomes which are designed to resemble natural bilayers in both composition and shape. They can encapsulate drugs to increase their bioavailability and target certain cells or tissues. Bilosomes are nanovesicular structures that contain bile salts and are utilised to deliver poorly permeable and highly lipophilic drugs. [4], [5]. They are spherical, unilamellar, and multilamellar vesicles having sizes ranging from 5 to 200 nm [1]. The capacity of bilosomes to prevent drugs or genetic material from degrading and improve its transport across cell membranes is one of its primary benefits. This might improve the bioavailability and efficacy of the encapsulated material. Additionally, they may be made to target certain tissues or cells, which can improve the therapy specificity [2]. Lipophilicity is a problem for many medications since it reduces their solubility in gastrointestinal (GI) fluids and, as a result, their bioavailability [3]. The majority of biological molecules, including proteins and peptides, as well as vaccines, undergo extensive degradation in the digestive tract,

making them ineffective when taken orally. Various tactics have been employed to tackle the limitations of traditional delivery techniques. Liposomes and niosomes are two examples of innovative vesicular carrier drug delivery technologies that can partially stop the degradation of the enclosed components. The new modified form of liposomes and niosomes known as bilosomes has the added benefit of bile salts, which increase their flexibility, absorption, and permeation. Both liposomes and niosomes are vesicular drug delivery systems, but they differ in terms of composition, structure, and properties. Phospholipids, which can be synthetic or natural, are amphiphilic molecules with a hydrophilic head and a hydrophobic tail. In aqueous environments, these phospholipids self-assemble into bilayer structures, forming vesicles with aqueous cores surrounded by lipid bilayers. Niosomes are vesicular structures that resemble liposomes, with aqueous cores enclosed by surfactant bilayers. Liposomes formed by phospholipids tend to be more stable due to the presence of natural phospholipids with well-defined structures and packing arrangements, but they may be susceptible to degradation by enzymes in biological fluids. This is mainly because non-ionic surfactants may undergo phase transitions or degradation under specific conditions. Non-ionic surfactants, like polyethylene glycol, typically have a hydrophilic head (like polyethylene glycol) and a hydrophobic tail (like alkyl chains) [6]. Bilosomes increase the biocompatibility and therapeutic efficacy of drugs because of their stability in the stomach [7]. Within the body, bile acids exist as ionised bile salts and are produced in the liver and stored in the gall bladder. Bile salts that are integrated into bilosomes, such as sodium taurocholate, sodium deoxycholate, and sodium glycocholate, are amphiphilic and therefore improve the systems penetration properties. This leads to an increase in the oral bioavailability and biodistribution of medications that have limited aqueous solubility and permeability [8], [9]. Bilosomes have several benefits, chief among them being the prevention of drug degradation and the improvement of their transmembrane transport. To improve the specificity of the treatment, they can also be made to target certain cells or tissues [2]. The inconsistency and susceptibility of bilosomes to preparation conditions is one of the main obstacles. Anticancer, CNS, protein/peptide, vaccination, and phytoconstituent drug delivery are among the well-established therapeutic uses of bilosomes as drug delivery vehicles. [10].

Figure 1 Structure of Bilosomes

ADVANTAGES:

- 1)The inclusion of non-ionic surfactants makes bilosomes both chemically and physically stable.[11]
- 2)They are biocompatible, biodegradable, non-toxic, and non-immunogenic.[11]
- 3) Bilosomes can be used to deliver genetic material to cells, which has the potential to be used in gene therapy. It can be difficult and time-consuming to prepare bilosomes, requiring specialised tools and knowledge.
- 4)They are able to contain both lipophilic and hydrophilic medications. [12]
- 5)It prevents the metabolic enzymes at the tear/corneal epithelial surface and in the GIT from breaking down drugs since bile is present.[13]
- 6) Bilosomal components don't need any particular handling techniques or handling issues.

DISADVANTAGES:

- 1) There are currently just a few drugs and genetic materials that employ bilosomes.
- 2) The efficacy of bilosomes may be impacted by their short shelf life and potential integrity loss.[14], [15]
- 3) It can be difficult and time-consuming to prepare bilosomes, requiring specialised tools and knowledge.
- 4) Temperature and storage conditions can have an impact on Bilosomal stability and integrity.

2. STRUCTURE AND COMPOSITION OF BILOSOMES:

Bilosomes are spherical in shape and amphiphilic in nature. Because they are amphiphilic, they can incorporate hydrophilic and lipophilic medicines, which are encased in bilayered membranes on the outside and an inside hydrophilic compartment.[16]

Bilosomes consist of a non-ionic surfactant, bile salt, lipophilic materials such as phospholipids and cholesterol, and other additives.

2.1 NON-IONIC SURFACTANT:

Because non-ionic surfactants have benefits over anionic, cationic, or amphoteric forms in terms of compatibility, stability, and toxicity, they are frequently utilised as surface-active agents during the manufacture of bilosomal materials. They are harmless, have little irritating impact on the surfaces of cells, and aid in maintaining the solutions physiological pH. Two areas make up the non-ionic surfactants chemical structure: one is lipid-like (hydrophobic) and the other is water-like (hydrophilic). These two regions are connected by ether, amide, or ester bonds.[17]

Furthermore, non-ionic surfactants function as strong P-glycoprotein inhibitors, obstructing drug efflux from cells. They allow for targeted administration of medication to certain tissues and aid with the absorption of medications. Since non-ionic surfactants have both polar and non-polar regions, they have a high degree of interfacial activity. It has been determined that surfactants with an HLB between 14 and 17 are not appropriate for the synthesis of Bilosomal vesicles. On the other hand, it has been demonstrated that an HLB value of 8.6 offers the highest level of entrapment efficacy. The HLB value drops from 8.6 to 1.7, which results in a fall in entrapment efficiency. For the goal of producing vesicles, non-ionic surfactants such as sorbitan fatty acid esters, alkyl glyceryl ethers, and alkyl esters are frequently utilised [15]

The primary factor affecting the vesicles capacity to encapsulate the drug is the hydrophilic lipophilic balance (HLB) value of the non-ionic surfactants that are used to make their membranes. Additionally, the length of the chain and the size of the hydrophilic head group of the non-ionic surfactants affect the drugs entrapment efficiency.[18]

As the surfactants HLB value decreases, the percentage of entrapment efficiency decreases. [19]

The commonly used non-ionic surfactants for bilosomes formation are as follows:

- Polyoxyethylene sorbitan fatty acid ester (Tweens).
- Polyethylene glycol hexadecyl ether and octadecyl ether (Brij 58- Brij S10).
- Sorbitan fatty acid ester (Spans).

2.2 BILE SALTS:

Bile acids are amphiphilic because they include methyl groups on one side that represent the hydrophobic side chain and hydroxyl groups on the other side that represent the side chain that loves water. Their ability to destabilize membranes allows them to function as both penetration enhancers and solubilising agents, which can improve drug absorption through a variety of routes.[20]

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Bile acids have the potential to integrate into biological membranes phospholipid, increasing membrane permeability and as a result, improving the absorption of drug that favour fat via the plasma membrane, increasing the oral bioavailability of several drugs. [21]

Bile salts are crucial in augmenting the drugs oral bioavailability in the gastrointestinal tract (GIT) because they thwart the bile salts lysis and deformation.

Bile salts such as sodium deoxycholate (SDC) are examples of substances used in bilosomal fabrications.

- Taurocholate (STC) of sodium.
- Chalcone (sodium).
- SGC, or sodium glycocholate.
- STDC, or sodium taurodeoxycholate.[22]

2.3 Cholesterol:

As cholesterol is added to the bilosome formulations, it becomes an amphiphilic molecule.

It is possible for cholesterol and non-ionic surfactants to interact. Thus, it may have an impact on bilosomes physical makeup and characteristics.[17]

The phase state of the lipid bilayer, which is influenced by the lipid composition, determines how cholesterol affects the bilosome membrane. In multi-component lipid mixtures, cholesterol induces phase separations by selectively partitioning between different coexisting

proteins, causing them to alter their conformation or relocate inside the membrane. As a result, increasing cholesterol makes bilosomes more stiff.[23],[24],[25]

Additionally, cholesterol is added to bilosomal formulations to change their mechanical strength and water permeability as well as to provide their bilayer membrane stiffness. The maximum allowable cholesterol percentage is mostly established by the non-ionic surfactant HLB value. When non-ionic surfactants have an HLB value more than ten, more cholesterol must be added in order to balance the higher head groups.

Figure 2 Structure of cholesterol

2.4 Phospholipids:

The primary constituents of the cellular membrane are phospholipids. They have the ability to self-assemble due to their amphiphilic nature, which causes them to become moist and emulsified. The amphiphilic nature of the phospholipids allows them to form closed, concentric bilayers when water is present. They effectively emulsify and are biocompatible with the cellular membrane. Glycerophospholipids and sphingomyelins are the two forms of phospholipids that are distinguished by the types of alcohol they contain. Phospholipids can also come from a variety of sources, including hydrogenated phosphatidylcholine, synthetic phosphatidylcholine, and natural phosphatidylcholine from egg yolks or soybeans. They can achieve wetting and emulsification processes because of their amphiphilic characteristic. Furthermore, the phospholipid plays a significant part in the production of vesicles and is in charge of the bilayer hardness.[26]

Examples of phospholipids:[27]

- Dipalmitoyl Phosphatidylcholine

- Dilauroyl Phosphatidylglycerol
- Distearoyl Phosphatidylglycerol
- Dioleoyl Phosphatidylglycerol
- Soybean Phosphatidylcholine
- Dimyristoyl Phosphatidylglycerol
- Dioleoyl Phosphatidylglycerol
- Soybean Phosphatidylcholines

3. METHODS OF PREPARATION:

3.1 Reverse phase evaporation method:

The reverse phase evaporation method is also called as the film reverse phase evaporation. It creates emulsions of water and oil in which the medication is present in the water phase and lipids form the organic phase to form a bilosomal bilayer.

This approach involves dissolving bile salts and soybean phosphatidylcholine in an organic solvent, such as absolute ether, and then slowly adding a protein-containing buffer solution drop by drop. For five minutes, the mixture is sonicated in a water bath without creating an emulsion.

To eliminate the organic solvent, the emulsion is rotavaporated at a speed of 50 revolutions per minute. After that, a buffer is added to the dry lipids to hydrate them and create a homogenous dispersion. After that, the dried lipids are mixed with a buffer to hydrate them and create a homogenous dispersion. To create bilosomes filled with the medication, this dispersion is lastly extruded through a high-pressure homogeniser, followed by ultracentrifugation for further purification.[28]

Figure 3 Reverse phase evaporation method

After that, the size, stability, and encapsulation efficiency of the finished product are assessed. Organic solvent residues can disrupt the chemical or biological stability of lipids or loaded pharmaceuticals is the disadvantage of this method

3.2. Thin Film Hydration Method:

The lipid component, soybean phosphatidylcholine, and the drug are dissolved in an organic solvent before being evaporated under decreased pressure using a rotary vacuum evaporator in order to prepare drug-loaded bilosomes via the thin film hydration process. After that, the thin film is hydrated with bile salt-containing buffer to create big multilamellar vesicles, which are subsequently reduced in size to tiny unilamellar vesicles by means of high pressure homogenisation. After that, these vesicles are purified to produce drug-loaded bilosomes.[21] High trapping effectiveness while using hydrophobic medications is the advantage of this method.

Demerit:

- Exposure to high temperatures may cause phospholipid and/or drug damage.
- challenging to scale up

3.3. Hot Homogenization Method:

The lipid components, such as mono palmitoyl glycerol, cholesterol, and dicetyl phosphate, are melted at 140°C for five minutes in order to prepare bilosomes using the hot homogenisation process. After that, they are hydrated with buffer solution. After homogenising the mixture, bile salt solution is added to create a dispersion that contains empty vesicles, and the mixture is homogenized once again. The homogenate is then mixed with the antigen buffered solution, and several Freeze Thaw cycles are used to entrap the protein. In order to reduce extended exposure to homogenisation, antigen is introduced at the very end.[29], [30]

3.4. Ether Injection Method:

The ether injection method, which is based on injecting an organic solvent, such ether, into an aqueous solution of phospholipids and bile salts, is a technique for making bilosomes.

The following steps are usually involved in the process:

Phospholipids and bile salts are combined into an aqueous solution at the proper pH and temperature. Next, a syringe or other similar instrument is used to inject an organic solvent, such as ether, into the aqueous solution. After that, the mixture is stirred or sonicated to create bilosomes. Phospholipids and bile salts self-assemble into bilosomes in response to the agitation.

There are restrictions with the reverse phase evaporation technique as well. Utilising organic solvents can be hazardous and have an impact on the bilosomes characteristics. Furthermore, the technique might not work with all kinds of enclosed materials.[31]

Figure 4 Ether Injection Method

4 CHARACTERIZATION OF BILOSOMES:

4.1. Entrapment Efficiency (%):

The percentage of the drug that is effectively entrapped or encapsulated inside the vesicles is known as the entrapment efficiency. A concomitant rise in bile salt concentration improves the drug's solubility in the dispersion media and its effectiveness of trapping. The percentage of the entrapped drug was calculated by indirect method using the following formula.[32]

Entrapment Efficiency % = $(\text{Total amount of drug} - \text{Total amount of free drug}) \times 100 / \text{Total amount of drug}$.

UV spectroscopy and high performance liquid chromatography are two spectroscopic or chromatographic techniques that may be used to measure entrapment effectiveness.[21]

4.2. Polydispersity Index (PDI):

The degree of non-uniformity in the particle size distribution is referred to as polydispersity. A homogenous population of phospholipid vesicles is indicated by a PDI of 0.3 or below, which is considered acceptable in drug delivery applications using lipid-based carriers, such as liposome and Nano-liposome formulations.[33]

4.3. Zeta Potential (ZP):

The overall charge that particles in a particular medium have gathered is known as the zeta potential. Compared to uncharged vesicles, those having a surface charge are more resilient against accumulation. Bile salts, which increase zeta potential and prevent vesicle aggregation, give bilosomes their negative charge.[34] By analysing the electrophoretic mobility in an electrical field with a Zetasizer, dynamic light scattering technology, nanoZS-90 Zetasizer, or Malvern Zetasizer equipment, it is a crucial characteristic that establishes the stability of the bilosomal dispersions. [34]. Furthermore, ZP levels decline even more when cholesterol concentrations rise. This is because cholesterol transfers to the membrane of the generated vesicles, causing a decrease in fluidity and an increase in stiffness. The arrangement of non-ionic surfactant chains and the membrane's stability both increase with elevated cholesterol contents. [35]

4.4. Ultracentrifugation:

Ultracentrifugation is a separation method that uses a high-speed centrifuge that can spin a rotor at a very high speed and create acceleration up to 10,00,000 g (about 9800 km/s²).. It has the ability to differentiate drug-loaded bilosomes from non-encapsulated drug. [21]

4.5. Particle Size:

Bilosomes have vesicles that range in size from 90nm to 3 μ m. In the Peyer's patches, larger bilosome vesicles (~6 μ m versus 2 μ m in diameter) shown increased uptake. The dynamic light scattering principle-based analytical tools, such as photon correlation spectroscopy, are utilised to calculate the particle size dispersion of bilosome vesicles. [36], [37]

4.6. stability Study:

One crucial factor in determining the stability of the generated vesicles is a stability study. It is important to look for many kinds of stability in bilosomal vesicles, including chemical, biological, and physical stability. The primary stability issues related to vesicle storage are

drug aggregation, fusion, and leakage.[17] The International Council for Harmonisation (ICH) guidelines provide the following storage conditions for stability studies:

- Long term stability study: $25\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}/60\%\pm 5\% \text{ RH}$ or $30\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}/65\%\pm 5\% \text{ RH}$.
- $40\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C} /75\%\pm 5\% \text{ RH}$ for an accelerated stability condition

4.7. Morphological Study:

Study of Morphology Microscopic analysis is frequently used to characterize the appearance and structure of the bilosomal vesicle. Many electron microscopic methods, including Scanning Electron Microscopy, which is used for formulations in the solid state, may be used to characterize binary vesicles. Transmission Electron Microscope, specifically for liquid-state bilosomal vesicles.[38], [39]

5 APPLICATION OF BILOSOMES:

5.1. Transdermal drug delivery system:

A long-acting NSAID called tenoxicam (TX) is used to treat rheumatic illnesses. The adverse effects of TX include GI ulceration, vomiting, dyspepsia, indigestion, and stomach discomfort. Transdermal penetration of TX was low. Regarding the foundation for the study done by Al-mahallawi et al., Bilosomes shown the capacity to enhance TX transdermal transport, preventing needless GI adverse effects correlated with oral delivery[21]

5.2. Cancer therapy:

Anticancer drugs have been suggested to be delivered by bilosomes as they can target certain cancer cells and increase the drug bioavailability.

5.3. Antiviral therapy:

Antiviral medications have been suggested to be delivered using bilosomes as they can both increase the drug bioavailability and prevent them from degrading.

5.4. Improved hypoglycemic activity:

Due to the harmful conditions in the GI tract, sodium glycocholate(SGC), a strong permeability enhancer and GI enzyme inhibitor, did not have any boosting impact on free rhINS absorption. Despite the presence of SGC, if recombinant human insulin rhINS had been released and exposed to the GI environment, it would have been fully digested and would not have had a hypoglycemia impact. Despite the presence of SGC, if rhINS had been released and exposed

to the GI environment, it would have been fully digested and would not have had a hypoglycemic impact [57, 58]. The outcomes showed that SGC with bilosomes preserved the vesicles' integrity and the encapsulated rhINS bioactivity.[40]

5.5. Bilosomes as drug delivery system for brain disorders:

The main obstacle preventing innovative treatments from penetrating the central nervous system is the blood–brain barrier (BBB) [41], [42]. Three biological elements of the brain microvasculature make up the blood-brain barrier (BBB): pericytes, astrocyte end-feet, and endothelial cells. It is intriguing to investigate the potential function of bile acids in neurodegenerative illnesses due to their oral bioavailability and ability to pass through microvascular endothelial cells in the human brain [43], [44]. To target specific brain regions, CNS medications with low therapeutic effectiveness can be encased in bilosomes. If these formulations are taken orally or intranasally, their bioavailability may be improved. Resveratrol (RES)-loaded bilosomes were created by Abbas et al to be used orally to treat Alzheimer's disease (AD). The well-known bioactive polyphenol molecule resveratrol (RES) is utilised to treat AD, yet its limited water solubility limits its practical application [45].

97% of the drug released from RES-loaded bilosomes was shown to be released in vitro, but only 25% of the drug was released from RES solution after two hours[46].

5.6. Ophthalmology:

In order to prevent drug degradation and improve drug transport across the cornea, bilosomes have been suggested as a delivery mechanism for ocular medications.

5.7. Neurology:

Medications for neurological illnesses have been proposed to be delivered using bilosomes, which can both preserve the medications from degradation and improve their transport over the blood-brain barrier.

5.8. Biomedical imaging:

In imaging procedures including computed tomography (CT) scans and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), bilosomes can be employed as contrast agents. Agriculture: Plant growth can be enhanced and pest and disease resistance can be achieved by using bilosomes.[47], [48], [49]

5.9. Ocular drug delivery:

Due to the short corneal residence time and quick removal of the injected dosage via the nasolacrimal drainage system, the traditional method of ocular drug administration has poor

bioavailability[50]. The adverse impact is a primary consideration when creating a drug delivery system for ocular illnesses since the eye is a fragile and sensitive human organ[51]. Topical gelling methods are being investigated as a potential solution to these constraints and as a means of enhancing ocular delivery, especially distribution to the anterior portion. It is claimed that the incorporation of drug-loaded bilosomes into an in situ gelling system is superior to conventional drug delivery techniques for the treatment of ocular disorders because it improves transcorneal flux, ocular residence time, controlled drug release, bioavailability, and ocular permeability. The ocular administration of bilosomes containing the ion-sensitive in situ gel of the antifungal drug natamycin was examined by Janga et al. The efficient absorption of natamycin-loaded bilosomes by the eyes was demonstrated by a six to nine-fold increase in their transcorneal flow.

5.10. Bilosomes for delivery of oral vaccines:

In terms of vaccine delivery, oral dosage is the gold standard for patient compliance.

Due to low absorption, the oral route is not advised for the majority of biologicals and vaccinations, although being highly favoured. Orally injected vaccinations get diluted, degraded by enzymes, and rejected by an epithelial barrier after becoming entrapped in the mucus gel of GI tract epithelia. This results in a weakened immune response. A delivery mechanism that can resist the deterioration in the stomach and intestine is still lacking. Bilosomes have been observed to be significantly more resilient in the acid and enzymes of the stomach [30], [53]. Bilosomes have also been proven to be an efficient formulation for oral medicinal administration as they have the ability to destabilize membranes due to the presence of bile salts. [54]

5.11. Bilosomes for Delivery of Proteins and Peptides:

Peptides and proteins provide a powerful therapeutic substitute for traditional small drugs in a number of illnesses. Large molecules have a short biological half-life, low patient compliance, and require technical skills to deliver, despite their better therapeutic effectiveness when given parenterally. A poor bioavailability of fewer than 10% resulted from oral administration of proteins and peptides with molecular weights more than 700 Da, which demonstrated poor stability in the GIT environment and inadequate intestinal barrier penetration. Protein and peptide delivery limitations can be overcome by employing vesicular nanocarriers, such as liposomes or niosomes, which have the ability to transport both hydrophilic and hydrophobic molecules. On the other hand, reports of vesicular nanocarrier instability, leakage, and low permeability in the GI environment exist. Moreover, gastric leakage denatures the peptides

by exposing them to GI enzymes [55]. Thus, the invention of a modified vesicular system known as bilosomes was prompted by the need for an alternate dosage form that can lessen the problems related to vesicular nanocarriers. Bile salts are included into the bilayer of bilosomes to stabilise the vesicular nanocarrier and stop leaks in the stomach environment. Bile salts also cause the bilayer to become more fluid, which enhances permeability across the GI membrane [56]. The capacity of regular liposomes and liposomes containing bile salts (sodium glycocholate) to encapsulate insulin and stop gastric leakage was examined in a research by Hu et al. [57]. Both *ex vivo* and artificial gastrointestinal fluids were used in the study. The study findings showed that, in comparison to ordinary liposomes, liposomes prepared with bile salts provided superior protection and reduced gastrointestinal leakage [57].

6 MARKETED PRODUCTS OF BILOSOMES:

1) Abraxane is a chemotherapeutic medication used to treat pancreatic, non-small cell lung, and breast cancers. It is also known as paclitaxel protein-bound particles for injectable solution. It is contained in bilosomes, which lessen adverse effects and help the medication target cancer cells.

2) Acute lymphoblastic leukaemia (ALL) is treated with the chemotherapeutic medication marqibo (vincristine sulphate LIPOSOME injection).

3) A chemotherapy medication called Doxil (doxorubicin hydrochloride liposome injection) is used to treat breast and ovarian malignancies. It is included in bilosomes, which lessen adverse effects and aid in the medication's targeting of cancer cells.

4) Adults with compensated liver disease who have a chronic hepatitis B virus (HBV) infection can be treated with a nucleotide reverse transcriptase inhibitor (NRTI) called Vemlidy (Tenofovir Alafenamide).[58], [59], [60]

7 CONCLUSION:

In this study, the most recent developments in the use of bilosomes as a nano-vesicular drug delivery method are discussed. There are several challenges in medication administration, including low solubility, poor penetration, poor absorption, the hepatic first-pass impact, drug degradation by metabolic enzymes, and low bioavailability. As a result of their usefulness in boosting drug solubility, membrane permeability, and bioavailability, bilosomes are emerging as a modern and efficient drug delivery method. Furthermore, because they can carry both fat- and water-loving medicines, bilosomes provide several superior benefits over traditional drug

delivery methods. They also allow for regulated, targeted, and successful drug administration. Although they have numerous benefits, bilosomes are a potential medication delivery method with several drawbacks. To completely grasp their potential and solve some of the issues related to their utilisation, more study is required. Furthermore, additional research is required to assess the effectiveness and safety of bilosomes in a range of therapeutic contexts. Even with these drawbacks, bilosomes have the ability to completely change how genetic materials and medications are absorbed by the body's cells and tissues, which is why the field of drug delivery is actively researching and developing bilosomes.

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